

A STUDY ON VIEWERS PREFERENCE TOWARDS ADVERTISEMENT

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Abstract:

Advertising is "a paid, mediated, form of communication from an identifiable source, designed to persuade the reader to take some action, now or in the future". A sample of 200 respondents were randomly selected for this study from Theni District. The selected samples were analyzed using simple percentage, ANOVA and t-test. It is found that using ANOVA and t-test there exists any significant association between gender, age, educational qualification, monthly income have significant difference in the level of Viewer's preference towards advertisement.

Key Words: Consumer, Preference, Attitude, Advertisement, Health & Fertilizer Etc.,

Introduction:

Advertising is "a paid, mediated, form of communication from an identifiable source, designed to persuade the reader to take some action, now or in the future." The term "mediated" means, simply, that some medium like television or newspaper or even the Internet conveys the message from sender to receiver, as opposed to direct "in-person" communication. The term "identifiable source" distinguishes advertising from wholly anonymous communications, such as those found in some unsolicited e-mail. The "action" can be buying a product or service, but it also can be directed at voting behavior during an election, or it might even entail not-for-profit social behavior like recycling, saving your money, saving the whales, or preventing abortion. Of course, one aspect of this definition that clearly makes it stand apart from most concepts of journalism is the phrase "designed to persuade". The term advertising is derived from the Latin word *advertere* which means 'to turn' the attention. Every piece of advertising turns the attention of the readers or the listeners or the viewers or the onlookers towards a product or a service or an idea. Therefore, it can be said that anything that turns the attention to an article or a service or an idea might be well called as advertising.

Advertising in India:

The history of advertising in India parallels the history of the Indian Press. The first issue of the first newspaper of the Indian subcontinent, was the 'Bengal Gazette' or the 'Calcutta General Advertiser', started by James Augustus Hicky on January 29, 1780. During the early years the newspapers announced births, deaths, appointments, arrival and departure of ships and sale of furniture. By the beginning of the 19th century the pattern of advertising revealed a definite change.

Even the daily newspapers announced themselves through advertisements in existing periodicals. The power of advertising increased rapidly with the growth in trade and commerce. By 1830, around three dozen newspapers and periodicals were being published on a regular basis from India. With the rise of new industries, advertising, even from British companies, increased. The growth of advertising in India is also linked to the Swadeshi movement (1920-1922), which gave impetus to Indian industries.

The first Indian ad agency, the Indian Advertising Agency, was launched in the very early years of the 20th century. On the other hand, B Dattaram & Co, located in Girgaum in Mumbai and launched in 1905, also claims to be the oldest existing Indian agency. This was followed by the launch of the Calcutta Advertising Agency in 1909. By the 1920s a number of Indian agencies were working from the major Indian cities, the most important being the Modern Publicity Company in Madras, Central Publicity Service in Bombay and Calcutta and the Oriental Advertising Agency in Tiruchirappalli.

In 1931, the first full-fledged Indian ad agency, the National Advertising Service, was established. During the post independence era, the advertising business was well on its way to growth and expansion. The Indian Society of Advertisers was formed in 1951 and in May 1958, the Society of Advertising Practitioners was established and advertising clubs came up in Bombay and Calcutta to promote higher standards of work. Market research and readership surveys led to further professionalisation of the advertising industry.

Television Rating Points, popularly known as TRP measurements, provided ad agencies with statistical data on consumer/ viewer likes and dislikes and helped them create effective media plans and ad campaigns. The introduction of multi-colour printing, improved printing machines and the development of commercial art gave the ad business a further boost. The advertising agencies expanded their services and this was due to the phenomenal growth in media. Besides selling space in newspapers and magazines, they began to offer artworks, organization of fairs and exhibitions and market research.

Review of Literature:

Brad J. Bushman and Angelica M. Benacci (2002) have carried out a study entitled “Violence and sex impair memory for Television Advertisement” pointed that participants watched a violent. Sexually explicit, or neutral TV program that contained a ads participants recalled the advertised brands, they also, identified the advertised brands from slides of super markets shelves.

Nidhi Kotwal, Neelima Gupta and Arjee Devi (2002) have carried out a study entitled “Impact of T.V. advertisements on buying pattern of adolescent girls” This study revealed that television and advertising together present a lethal combination and has become an integral part of modern society. The present study was conducted on 100 adolescent girls, studying in class 9th – 12th, to know the impact of T.V. advertisement of their buying pattern. It is the most convenient route to reach not only adult viewers but also the adolescents. Adolescents are manipulated by advertisement promise that the product will do something special for them which will transform their life.

John H. Murphy and Gary B. Wilcox (2002) have carried out a study entitled that” The impact of program environment on recall of humorous television commercials”, pointed that investigated that the possible effect of television program types on the recall performance of humorous television commercials. An experimental design was developed to test the relative performance of the same humorous and non-humorous ads in three different contextual environments-situation comedy, action/adventure, and documentary. The findings indicate that the recall performance of commercials and of the product or service promoted are both affected by the program environment within which the ads appear.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To know the viewer’s attitude towards advertisement
- ✓ To determine the viewer’s preference towards advertisement in Theni District.

Research Methodology:

Theni District is the study area selected for this research. Primary data is collected through interview schedule. Samples of 200 viewers in Theni District have been selected by purposive sampling method. The collected information were reviewed and consolidated into a master table. For the purpose of analysis the data were further processed by using statistical tools. The statistical tools are

- ✓ Simple Percentage
- ✓ ANOVA
- ✓ t-test

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is restricted to the selected sample of Theni District and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.
- ✓ The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Viewers

Factors	Number of Viewers N=200	Percentage
Gender		
Male	50	25
Female	150	75
Age (Years)		
Up to 25	52	26
26 to 50	84	42
Above 50	44	22
Educational Qualification		
School Level	50	25
UG	86	43
PG	64	32
Occupation		
Agriculture	36	18
Employee	84	42
Business/Professional	38	19
House Wife	42	21
Monthly Income		
Up to Rs.10000	70	35
Rs.10000 to Rs.25000	96	48
Above Rs.25000	34	17
Type of Family		

Joint Family	110	55
Nuclear Family	90	45

Table 1 describes the demographic profile of the TV viewers. Out of 200 viewers who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (75%) of the viewers are female, (42%) whose age group is under 26 to 50 years, most (43%) of the viewers are UG, maximum number (42%) of viewers are employee, the monthly income of (48%) viewers are Rs.10,001 to Rs.25,000 and (55%) viewers belong to joint family

Table 2: Relationship between Demographic Profile and Viewers Preference towards advertisement

Variables	Statistical Test	Value	Result
Gender and level of preference towards advertisement	t-test	t=8.19	S
Age and level of preference towards advertisement	ANOVA	F=5.949	S
Educational Qualification and level of preference towards advertisement	ANOVA	F=13.37	S
Occupation and level of preference towards advertisement	ANOVA	F=16.34	NS
Type of Family and level of preference towards advertisement	t-test	t=0.57	NS
Monthly Income and level of preference towards advertisement	ANOVA	F=13.86	S

*significant at 5% percent level

Table no.2 depicts there is a significant difference in the level of preference towards advertisement among gender of viewers. There is a significant difference in the level of preference towards advertisement among age groups of the viewers. There is a significant difference in the level of preference towards advertisement among different educational qualification of the viewers. There is no significant difference in the level of preference towards advertisement among different occupation of the viewers. There is no significant difference in the level of preference towards advertisement among viewers type of family. There is a significant difference in the level of preference towards advertisement among viewers monthly income.

Findings of the Study:

- ✓ Most of the viewers are female.
- ✓ Most of the viewer's age is between 26 to 50 years.
- ✓ Majority of the viewers are employees.
- ✓ Most of the viewers are under graduates.
- ✓ Using ANOVA and t-test it is found that there exists any significant association between gender, age, educational qualification, monthly income have significant difference in the level of Viewer's preference towards advertisement.

Conclusion:

In the modern day the wants of people are progressively increasing. They are in need of many products. To fulfill the customers many manufacturers enter into the market. Most of the manufacturers give advertisement to make awareness among the public. The advertisement is capable of capturing the minds of customers for each and every product many brands of available in the market. At the time of shopping the customers must be able to recall the brand name of the product they want. So the manufacturers must keep in mind while making advertisement how to attract customers. It will increase the goodwill for their product as well as profit.

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